

Second Phase of China-Pakistan Free Trade Deal in Effect

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

China is the biggest Economy in the world and as well as big trading hub for Asian countries. In this paper we will study about targeting exports and Imports countries form the Whole world for Pakistan and China. How CPEC it will be more successful for both countries Pakistan and China. Because CPEC is a short way and the most important benefit for China under CPEC is to reduce China's trade routes from the existing sea routes from 12,000 kilometers to 2,000 kilometers. It is expected that the domestic trade between Pakistan and China will undergo major changes. And also reduce the total expensive of actual price of transportation. In this paper we study about the second phase of free trade agreement (FTA) which will be more bilateral trade and its benefits for both countries businessman to selling product in china and Pakistan. China has granted Pakistan to imports 783 duty free products without tariff lines that do not impose zero percent tariffs in CPFTA-I. And in this new phase CPFTA-II Pakistani manufacturers and traders will be able to export about 313 new products to the Chinese market without tariffs. In this research we contain the latest international trade data for China and Pakistan including service trade data, and tariffs.

Keywords: *CHINA PAKISTAN ECONOMICS CORRIDOR (CPEC), CHINA-PAKISTAN FREE TRADE AGREEMENT (CPFTA), BILATERAL TRADE BETWEEN PAKISTAN AND CHINA.*

1. Introduction

The second phase of the China-Pakistan Free Trade Agreement came into effect in December 2019. In the new phase, Pakistani manufacturers and traders will be able to export about 313 new products to the Chinese market without tariffs. In this paper we, study China on implementing the second phase of the free trade agreement, which will improve bilateral trade and make it easier for Pakistani businessmen to export their products to the Chinese market without levying tariffs. Beijing had previously approved the premature launch of the second phase agreement with Pakistan, which was signed during Prime Minister Imran Khan's visit to China in April 2019. According to the first free trade agreement signed between the two countries in 2006, Pakistan has imposed zero tariffs on China on 724 products. After the implementation of the second agreement, Pakistan can export more than 1,000 products to China with zero tariffs in industry. The new

plant will be particularly beneficial to the agriculture, leather, candy and biscuit industries. Last year, Pakistan and China signed an agreement to use Chinese currency for bilateral trade, thereby reducing the burden of the U.S. dollar on bilateral trade (\$15 billion).

According to this study, Pakistan's bilateral trade volume increased from US\$2.2 billion in 2005 to US\$15.6 billion in fiscal year 2019. In April, Khan also announced the "next phase" of the project. He said that the billion-dollar economic cooperation with China will focus on eliminating poverty in Pakistan. During his visit to Beijing, Khan said: "Pakistan and China are entering the next stage of the China-EU economic cooperation plan, and will pay more attention to socio-economic improvement, poverty alleviation, agricultural cooperation and industrial development." CPEC refers to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor, which is part of China's "One Belt One Road" initiative, an ambitious project that aims to connect Asia with Africa and Europe through land and sea networks to increase trade and stimulate the economy increase. The strategically important Xinjiang province in Northwest China is connected with Gwadar Port in Pakistan through a network of roads, railways and pipelines to transport cargo, oil and gas. Economic corridors will not only provide China with cheap access to Africa and the Middle East, but will also provide Pakistan with billions of dollars in transit facilities to the world's second largest economy. China has pledged to invest more than US\$60 billion in Pakistan under the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) project, which plans to build a series of special economic zones in Pakistan. India opposes CPEC because it was conducted through Pakistan-occupied Kashmir. When commenting on the second phase of the free trade agreement with Pakistan, Geng Shuang, a spokesman for the Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs, told the media that the core content of the agreement is greatly increase the level of liberalization of trade in goods. According to regulations, the share of tariff-free products and products without tariffs between China and Pakistan will gradually increase from 35% to 75%. In addition, both parties will reduce taxes by 20% on other products (5%) percentage of respective tariff lines. The tariff reduction measures will be implemented from January 1.

2. Overview

After seven years of negotiations on the China-Pakistan Free Trade Agreement, the agreement is an integral part of CPFTA2 and was signed in April 2019. Once implemented, the second phase of CPFTA will last for five years. This paper presents, only taking into account China's tariff concessions to Pakistan. Pakistan has provided HS with 8,238 tax numbers, and the tax rate is 8 digits. As shown in Table 1, these subsidies are divided into 7 categories. China has provided Pakistani exporters with immediate duty-free imports of 3,707 items, accounting for 45% of all tariff lines in CPFTA2. In addition to duty-free goods, there are two other categories, which must reduce tariffs to 0% within 5 and 10 years (A-5 and A-10, respectively). The preferential rate should be 20% lower than the basic tax rate of MOP 1 and MOP 2, and for the last two categories, the tariff rate will remain the basic tax rate of category 1 and 2 (no list of exemptions). By 2030, China will cut tariffs on all product lines by 75%.

Table 1 Description of CPFTA2 concessions offered to Pakistan by China

Category	Description	Tariff lines (HS 8-digits)	Tariff lines (per cent)
A-0	Duty-free access immediately	3707	45
A-5	Duty-free access by year 5	1235	15
A-10	Duty-free access by year 10	1236	15
MOP-1	Reduce base rates by 20 per cent in year 5	273	3
MOP-2	Reduce base rates by 20 per cent immediately	139	2
C-1	Tariffs remain at 2013 base rate	835	10
C-2	No concession (MFN rates apply)	813	10
Total lines		8238	100

Source: Ministry of Commerce (2019)

The most basic criterion for the quality of concession rights provided by China is how many types of tariff items it actually imports from the world. In 2018, China did not import 1,035 tariff lines (8-digit HS tax rate) from the world, nor was it 13% of the 8,238 tariff lines included in the second phase of the CPFTA. In the remaining 87% of product codes, the tariff rate ranges from 0 to 65%. China has granted immediate duty-free access to 3,707 lines (45% of all tariff lines). By 2030, 30% of the tariff lines will be exempted. Tariffs on 412 lines will be reduced by 20 per cent in five years, while tariffs will remain at base year (2013) rates for 1867 tariff lines (or 20 per cent of the tariff lines). (Table 1)

Other top-level features of the CPFTA2 (2019-2024) are outlined below (Ministry of Commerce, 2019).

1. China has granted Pakistan an immediate duty-free import for 783 tariff lines that do not impose a 0% tariff in CPFTA1.
2. Regarding the tariff breakdown of Pakistan's exports, there will be 845 tariff breakdowns by 2030 (based on HS 8-digit numbers).
3. At the same time, the 813 tariff categories for which China has not granted any preferential treatment belong to the second category. Tariffs ranging from 2% to 65% will be imposed on exports to China.
4. The guarantee clause has been included in the standards by FTAs around the world. If a balance of payments crisis occurs, Pakistan can impose tariffs.
5. Real-time electronic exchange of business data has been enabled to reduce false positives and insufficient invoices exposed in the first phase. This will reduce Pakistan's revenue loss.

The major features of the agreement in Phase-II inter-alia include:

i. Market Access: In the second phase of the CPFTA, the two countries will release 75% of tariff lines in their counterpart countries/regions within 10 years (to China) and 15 years (to Pakistan). China will immediately abolish tariffs on the priority tariffs for most of Pakistan's export benefits. In general, China has given preferential treatment to products including textiles and clothing, seafood, meat and other animal products, prepared foods, leather, chemicals, plastics, oils, footwear, and engineering products (including tractors and auto parts) Electrical appliances, machinery and many more. Pakistan provides access to raw

materials, intermediate products and machinery into the Chinese market. Access to cheaper imported inputs and machinery will increase Pakistan's export competitiveness and help increase its industrial production.

ii. Protected Tariff Lines: The 25% tariff line, 1760 TL, is already included in the protected list. The main industries protected include: textiles and clothing, steel, automobiles, electrical equipment, agriculture, chemicals, plastics, rubber, paper and cardboard, ceramics, glass and glassware, surgical instruments, footwear, leather, wood, objects, stones, and other products.

iii. Safeguard Measures: Invoking the "Safeguard Measures" (SGM) temporarily restrict the import of products that may cause harm or threaten to cause harm to domestic industries. The existing SGM in CPFTA is not enough to solve industry problems and has expired because these problems can only be called during the transition period (i.e., 2007-12). The following modifications have been incorporated into the agreement:

- a. In Phase-I SGM were limited to the absolute increase in imports, but now can be invoked on relative increase in imports as well.
- b. The transition period in has been increased to 10 years for CAT-I and 8 years for the remaining tracks, which in relation to Tariff Reduction Modality will be 15 years for CAT-II & 23 years for CAT-III.
- c. SGMs can be applied for 3 years, and can be extended to an additional 2 years. This has not been granted to any other country by China.
- d. In Phase-I SGM, injury to the industry had to be proven but an emergency measure of 180 days can be imposed in Phase-II without proving injury.

iv. Balance of Payment: This provision has been introduced in the Agreement as such measures can help to forestall the imminent threat of a serious decline in monetary reserves.

v. Electronic Data Exchange: In order to avoid false declarations and insufficient invoices imported from China, an electronic data interchange system has been implemented for ongoing trade under the framework of the Free Trade Agreement.

3. Literature review

The purpose of a literature review is for the researcher to take a critical look at the previous literature that already exists in the particular area that the researcher is searching. It will help the researcher on the intended topic and hope to explain the variables very well. The dependent and independent variables were discussed in detail below with appropriate literature review. The main idea of economic corridors is initiated from the concept of transport corridor. A transport corridor is a network within one country or between any two countries to connect economic centers (Khan et al. 2015).¹¹ Nogales et al. (2014) In an economic corridor, there are four different progressive stages, in which every former stage is included to the succeeding one using a more radical approach. It generally starts with infrastructure development and transport and then it moves to logistic corridors. Thus, transport corridor provides the foundation block for the latter stage corridors to come up. Logistic corridor then joins itself in the trade corridor. A trade corridor

leads to develop economic corridor which consequently results in improving economic growth.¹²

The literature which has shown up since the official declaration of China's investment in Pakistan in April 2015 appears to share common findings and that is positive impact of joining Gwadar and Xinjiang on both economies (Javid and Jahangir et. al 2015).¹³ Past researchers found that from 1970s onwards, the relationship between China and Pakistan fortified more among all the sectors (Shah et al. 2015).¹⁴ Study by Hiro and Itakura (2014)¹⁵ the following hypotheses have been developed:

- Pakistan- China FTA has significant impact on real GDP of a country.
- Pakistan- China FTA has significant impact on country's trade balance.
- Pakistan- China FTA effect on trade and output in different sectors within the country.
- Pakistan- China FTA has significant effect on country's welfare.

CPEC will directly generate an estimated 1.2 million jobs and crucial infrastructure in the energy, transportation, agricultural, health, and tourism sectors. Additionally, it will also provide much-needed Foreign-Direct-Investment (FDI) through the Special Economic Zones. These factors combined hold the potential to rescue Pakistan out of its financial woes and stir it towards a strong and self-reliant economy (Faraz Zia et al., 25 August 2020).¹⁶ Edwards & Odendaal (2019) investigated the impact of quality of infrastructure in exports. The results reveal that improving the quality of infrastructure in exports has a positive effect on exports by lowering the transport cost faced by the exporter. The results also suggest that it is the minimum quality of infrastructure between two trading countries that matter most for transport cost and trade.¹⁷

4. Research Methodology

In order to determine the impact of free trade agreements on the trade volume between Pakistan and China, data on the import and export and trade variables of cross-border countries from 2015 to 2020 have been collected. The study selected countries including China, the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, the United Arab Emirates, Taiwan, South Korea, Saudi Arabia, Hong Kong, Indonesia and Pakistan. The data is collected from the World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank database. In the study, the sum of imports and exports is regarded as trade volume, which is our dependent variable. This paper examines data that is qualitative and narrative in nature. These data are obtained from reliable secondary sources, including official documents, academic research, Journal Articles and social media, which emphasize the geographic importance of CPEC and intentionally influence. In order to achieve the purpose of this research, exploratory research methods are used to enhance understanding and demonstrate the strategic value of CPEC in the context of Pakistan and China.

This research is based upon the analysis of the annual data of 6 years i.e., 2015-2020. It also studies only the exports and Imports potential between both Countries Pakistan and China. Moreover, the study assessed the impact of the free trade agreement (free trade agreement) between Pakistan and China on the growth of Pakistan and China's exports, imports, and trade flows. This research is analytical in nature, based on North American Academic Research, 4(2) | 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4506802> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 5

archival data retrieved from Ministry of Commerce, Online resources, OEC (Observation of Economic Complexity), ITC (International Trade Center) and Trade Economics, these all sources is the world's leading data visualization platform for international trade data.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. International Trade of Pakistan and China

In recent years, China's international trade has boomed. The rise of China as a major participant in world trade is a major advancement in the world trading system. Due to China's "import substitution" strategy, China revised its trade development policy in the late 1970s, when China ranked 32nd among international trading nations. Now, China has become the world's leading exporter. China has become the world's largest commodity trading nation, ending the U.S. dominance in international trade after the war. There is no comparability between Pakistan and China in international trade. China should phase out backward industries that compete with ASEAN, such as high-pollution and resource-based industries, and strengthen cooperation with different countries and regions based on the characteristics of their respective countries and regions that's means, Economic structure and technical level. The optimization of the industrial structure will promote trade between China and ASEAN.

Table 2. Trade flows of Pakistan and China from 2016 to 2020

<i>Pakistan to World</i>					
<i>All Product</i>	<i>Value in 2015</i>	<i>Value in 2016</i>	<i>Value in 2017</i>	<i>Value in 2018</i>	<i>Value in 2019</i>
<i>Imports</i>	43,989,645	46,998,269	57,518,651	60,391,133	50,134,812
<i>Exports</i>	22,089,018	20,533,793	21,911,598	23,778,621	23,818,817
<i>World Trade Balance for Pakistan</i>					
<i>Trade Balance</i>	-21,900,627	-26,464,476	-35,607,053	-36,612,512	-26,315,995
<i>China to World</i>					
<i>Imports</i>	1,681,670,816	1,588,695,867	1,840,957,060	2,134,987,265	2,068,950,255
<i>Exports</i>	2,281,855,922	2,118,980,582	2,271,796,142	2,494,230,195	2,498,569,866
<i>World Trade Balance for China</i>					
<i>Trade Balance</i>	600,185,106	530,284,715	430,839,082	359,242,930	429,619,611
<i>Pakistan to China</i>					
<i>Imports</i>	11,019,005	13,680,153	15,404,325	14,599,749	12,423,997
<i>Exports</i>	1,934,926	1,590,858	1,510,410	1,829,435	2,042,893
<i>Trade Balance between Pakistan and China</i>					
<i>Trade Balance</i>	-9,084,079	-12,089,295	-13,893,915	-12,770,314	-10,381,104

<i>China to Pakistan</i>					
<i>Imports</i>	2,477,066	1,906,332	1,830,041	2,179,816	1,807,882
<i>Exports</i>	16,481,153	17,468,609	18,309,555	16,967,145	16,183,489
<i>Trade Balance between China and Pakistan</i>					
<i>Trade Balance</i>	14,004,087	15,562,277	16,479,514	14,787,329	14,375,607

Source: Author's own calculations based on ITC & UN COMTRADE statistics

However, Table 2 shows how China trades as much as multiple times more than what Pakistan does. In addition, China has emerged as an exports-driven nation with its growth rate of exports surpassing that of its imports. Pakistan's export growth rate is still lagging at the back its import growth rates.

5.2. Pakistan balance of trade

Pakistan announced a trade deficit of 283592 billion Pakistani rupees in October 2020. According to Trading Economics global macro models and analysts' expectations, by the end of the quarter; Pakistan's trade balance is expected to be -330000.00 PKR million. Looking ahead, we estimate that Pakistan's trade balance will be -319200.00 within 12 months. From a long-term perspective, according to our econometric model, Pakistan's trade balance is expected to reach -329000.00 million Pakistani rupees in 2021. From 1957 to 2020, Pakistan's trade balance averaged -47,583.93 PKR million, reached a record 6457 PKR million in June 2003, and reached a record -452668 PKR million in June 2018. The research provides: business: real value, historical data, forecasts, graphs, statistics, economic calendar and news. Pakistan's trade balance (data, historical charts, forecasts and release schedule) was last updated in November 2020. Tradingeconomics.com / General Administration of customs are given in Table 3. Furthermore, Figure 1 shows the China balance of trade for (2016 – 2020).

Figure 1 Pakistan Balance of Trade 2016 - 2020

Sources: Tradingeconomics.com / General Administration of customs

Table 3. Tradingeconomics / General Administration of customs

<i>Actual</i>	<i>Previous</i>	<i>Highest</i>	<i>Lowest</i>	<i>Dates</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
<i>-283592.00</i>	<i>-403393.00</i>	<i>6457.00</i>	<i>-452668.00</i>	<i>1957 - 2020</i>	<i>PKR Million</i>	<i>Monthly</i>
<i>Calendar</i>	<i>GMT</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>Actual</i>	<i>Previous</i>	<i>Consensus</i>	<i>TEForecast</i>
<i>2020-07-20</i>	<i>10:00 AM</i>	<i>Jun</i>	<i>PKR-352B</i>	<i>PKR-234B</i>		<i>PKR -168B</i>
<i>2020-08-17</i>	<i>10:00 AM</i>	<i>Jul</i>	<i>PKR-274B</i>	<i>PKR-350B</i>		<i>PKR -250B</i>
<i>2020-09-21</i>	<i>10:00 AM</i>	<i>Aug</i>	<i>PKR-284B</i>	<i>PKR -274B</i>		<i>PKR -230B</i>
<i>2020-10-19</i>	<i>10:00 AM</i>	<i>Sep</i>	<i>PKR-404B</i>	<i>PKR -290B</i>		<i>PKR -260B</i>
<i>2020-11-16</i>	<i>10:00 AM</i>	<i>Oct</i>		<i>PKR -404B</i>		<i>PKR -350B</i>
<i>2020-12-16</i>	<i>10:00 AM</i>	<i>Nov</i>				<i>PKR -340B</i>

Source: *Tradingeconomics.com*

Since 2003, Pakistan has been experiencing a stable trade deficit, mainly due to high energy imports. Since 2012, China has become Pakistan's largest trading partner to replace the United States. In recent years, the trade deficit with China, India, the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait and Malaysia has been the largest. Pakistan has a trade surplus with the United States, Afghanistan, Germany and the United Kingdom.

5.3. China Balance of Trade

By October 2020, China's trade surplus will increase from US\$42.3 billion in the same month last year to US\$58.44 billion, far higher than market expectations of US\$46 billion. Exports increased by 11.4%, while imports increased by 4.7%. The Country trade surplus with the US widened from 30.75 billion US dollars in September to 31.37 billion US dollars in October. Taking into account the first ten months of this year, the trade surplus was 384.5 billion U.S. dollars, exports increased by 0.5% year-on-year to 2.05 trillion U.S. dollars, while imports fell by 2%. , An increase of 3% to \$1.66 trillion.

According to Trading Economics global macro models and analysts' expectations, by the end of the quarter, China's trade balance will be 130.00 HML. Looking ahead, we estimate that China's trade balance will reach 570.00 within 12 months. From a long-term perspective, according to our econometric model, China's trade balance is expected to reach around 110.00 HML in 2021 and around 490.00 HML in 2022. From 1981 to 2020, China's trade balance averaged US\$108.23 HML, reached a record high of US\$630.33 HML in May 2020, and reached a record low of US\$-320.02 HML in February 2012. China's trade balance-actual value, are historical data, forecasts, graphs, statistics, economic calendar and news. China's trade balance (data,

historical charts, forecasts and release schedule) was last updated in November 2020. Tradingeconomics.com / General Administration of customs are given in Table 4. Furthermore, Figure 2 shows the China balance of trade for (2016 – 2020).

Figure 2. China Balance of Trade 2016 – 2020

Sources: Tradingeconomics.com / General Administration of customs

Table 4. Tradingeconomics/ General Administration of customs

<i>Actual</i>	<i>Previous</i>	<i>Highest</i>	<i>Lowest</i>	<i>Dates</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	
584.43	369.99	630.33	-320.02	1981 - 2020	USD HML	Monthly	<i>Current Prices, NSA</i>
<i>Calendar</i>	<i>GMT</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>Actual</i>	<i>Previous</i>	<i>Consensus</i>	<i>TEForecast</i>	
2020-08-07	03:00 AM	Jul	\$62.33B	\$46.42B	\$42B	\$41.9B	
2020-09-07	03:00 AM	Aug	\$58.93B	\$62.33B	\$50.5B	\$47B	
2020-10-13	03:00 AM	Sep	\$37B	\$58.93B	\$58B	\$ 60B	
2020-11-07	03:00 AM	Oct	\$58.44B	\$37B	\$46B	\$42B	
2020-12-07	03:00 AM	Nov		\$58.44B			

Source: Tradingeconomics.com

Since 1995, China’s trade surplus has remained stable and has doubled tenfold from 2004 to 2009. In 2019, China’s trade surplus was US\$421.9 billion, the largest since 2016. Due to weak domestic demand and trade tensions, exports increased by 0.5% and imports fell by 2.7% with the United States. The countries with the largest trade surpluses are the United States, Hong Kong and the European Union, especially the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Poland, Spain, Italy and Belgium, India, Vietnam, the Philippines, Singapore, the United Arab Emirates, Pakistan, Turkey and Indonesia. The countries with the largest trade deficits are Taiwan, Australia, South Korea, Brazil, Saudi Arabia, Japan, Germany, Switzerland, Malaysia, Oman, Chile and Russia.

[China October Trade Surplus Larger than Expected](#)

By October 2020, China's trade surplus will increase from US\$42.3 billion in the same month last year to US\$58.44 billion, far higher than market expectations of US\$46 billion. Exports increased by 11.4%, while imports increased by 4.7%. The US trade surplus with the US widened from 30.75 billion US dollars in September to 31.37 billion US dollars in October. Taking into account the first ten months of this year, the trade surplus was 384.5 billion U.S. dollars, exports increased by 0.5% year-on-year to 2.05 trillion U.S. dollars, while imports dropped 2.3 percent to USD 1.66 trillion.

[China Trade Surplus Smaller than Forecast](#)

In September 2020, China's trade surplus narrowed to 37 billion U.S. dollars from 39.1 billion U.S. dollars in the same month last year, the lowest level since March and well below market expectations of 58 billion U.S. dollars. As global demand continues to rebound from the impact of the pandemic, both imports and exports hit record highs. The country's trade surplus with the United States narrowed from US\$34.24 billion in August to US\$30.75 billion in September. In the first nine months of this year, China's trade surplus with the United States reached US\$218.57 billion.

[China Trade Surplus Larger than Expected](#)

In August 2020, China's trade surplus expanded significantly from 34.72 billion U.S. dollars in the same month last year to 58.93 billion U.S. dollars, much higher than market expectations of 50.5 billion U.S. dollars. Exports grew by 9.5%, the fastest rate since March last year, while imports unexpectedly fell by 2.1%. The country's trade surplus with the United States widened from US\$32.46 billion in July to US\$34.24 billion in August.

[China Trade Surplus Larger than Expected](#)

By July 2020, China's trade surplus has increased sharply from US\$44.02 billion in the same period last year to US\$62.33 billion, far higher than market expectations of US\$42 billion. Exports increased by 7.2%, the fastest rate since December last year, while imports unexpectedly fell by 1.4%. The country's trade surplus with the United States widened from US\$29.41 billion in June to US\$32.46 billion in July. The renewed tensions between China and the United States may affect trade data before the US presidential election in November. Meanwhile, Washington and Beijing will meet on August 15 to review the implementation of the first phase of the trade agreement reached earlier this year. Pakistan Exports and import to World, top Five Chapters (2015 – 2019) is given in Table 5 & 6.

Table 5. Pakistan Exports to World, top Five Chapters (2015 – 2019)

<i>HS4 Code</i>	<i>Product Label</i>	<i>Exported values in 2015</i>	<i>Exported values in 2016</i>	<i>Exported values in 2017</i>	<i>Exported values in 2018</i>	<i>Exported values in 2019</i>
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63	Other made-up textile articles; sets; worn clothing and worn textile articles; rags	3,759,721	3,803,987	3,961,922	4,076,838	4,070,644
52	Cotton	4,040,271	3,497,374	3,503,094	3,520,871	3,252,069
61	Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted	2,359,608	2,347,471	2,519,831	2,878,652	3,028,781
62	Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, not knitted or crocheted	2,127,462	2,253,021	2,469,150	2,599,885	2,814,503
10	Cereals	1,942,267	1,717,085	1,754,249	2,340,176	2,375,641

Source: Author's own calculations based on ITC & UN COMTRADE statistics

Table 6. China's Exports to World, top Five Chapters (2015 – 2019)

HS4 Code	Product Label	Exported values in 2015	Exported values in 2016	Exported values in 2017	Exported values in 2018	Exported values in 2019
85	Electrical machinery and equipment and parts thereof; sound recorders and reproducers, television.	600,292,287	557,061,947	598,974,916	664,425,033	670,997,854
84	Machinery, mechanical appliances, nuclear reactors, boilers; parts thereof	364,536,627	344,804,517	382,926,132	429,953,148	416,975,731
94	Furniture; bedding, mattresses, mattress supports, cushions and similar stuffed furnishings.	98,734,456	89,500,005	89,816,692	96,416,994	99,499,770
39	Plastics and articles thereof	65,835,653	64,035,659	70,645,690	80,135,877	84,386,942
87	Vehicles other than railway or tramway rolling stock, and parts and accessories thereof	62,651,637	60,416,649	67,358,135	75,094,321	74,366,536

Source: Author's own calculations based on ITC & UN COMTRADE statistics

5.4. Bilateral Trade between Pakistan and China

There is a clear imbalance in the trade between Pakistan and China, because Pakistan's imports are three times as much as exports to China. China's exports to Pakistan have grown faster than China's overall exports and overall imports from Pakistan. In other words, China is entering the Pakistani market much faster than any other export destination. The China-Pakistan Free Trade Agreement was signed in November 2006 to promote bilateral trade. According to the CPFTA, the two countries agreed to phase out or reduce the most favored nation tariffs in the 7,550 tariff lines of the 8-digit HS level. The agreement will be implemented in two five-year phases, with the first phase spanning 2007-12. The two parties agreed to reduce tariffs as part of the first phase, as shown in Table 7 below.

Table 7. Summary of concessions offered in CPFTA1 (2007-12)

Category	Tracks	Pakistan TRMs		China TRMs	
		# of TLS	% of TLS	# of TLS	% of TLS

i	Elimination of tariffs (3 years)	2423	35.6	2681	35.5
ii	0-5 per cent (5 years)	1338	19.9	2604	34.5
iii	50 per cent of margin of preference	157	2	604	8
iv	20 per cent of margin of preference	1768	26.1	529	7
v	No concession	1025	15	1132	15
vi	Exclusion list	92	1.4	-----	-----
	Total lines (at the HS 8-digit level)	6803		7550	

Source: Ministry of Commerce (2019)

The Figure 3 below illustrates the timelines and summarizes the concessions granted in both phases of the FTA.

Figure 3. Timeline of the CPFTA

5.5. Structure and volume of bilateral trade

Since the CPFTA, the total trade volume with China has grown rapidly and has tripled in 2018, reaching 16.4 billion U.S. dollars. However, despite the rapid growth in imports from China, exports from Pakistan have not been able to obtain similar benefits in China. Especially in the past, from years (2014-18), exports to China have fallen by 7% per year, while imports have grown at a rate of 12% per year. Although China's share of Pakistan's imports has grown much faster than its share of exports, China's share of Pakistan's imports and exports has also grown steadily. The value of total exports from Pakistan was \$ 23 billion in 2019. USA was the largest market for exports from Pakistan in 2019 (\$ 4.03 billion or 16.9% of total exports). The top exported product from Pakistan in 2019 (13.6%) was commodity group 6302 "Bed linen, table linen, toilet linen and kitchen linen." - The value of exports of this group amounted to \$ 3.25 billion.

Similarly, the value of total imports to Pakistan was \$ 50 billion in 2019. China was the largest supplier of goods to Pakistan in 2019 (\$ 12.4 billion or 24% of total merchandise imports). The top imported product to Pakistan in 2019 (10.7%) was commodity group 2710 "Petroleum oils and oils obtained from bituminous minerals, other than crude; preparations not elsewhere specified or included, containing by weight 70 % or more of petroleum oils or of oils obtained from bituminous minerals, these oils being the basic constituents of the preparations; waste oils." - The value of imports of this category was equal to 5.37 billion USD. Furthermore, an important direction of merchandise exports in Pakistan (2019) was precious. (See figure 7 and 8) In terms of the composition of Pakistan's exports to China, several export categories are growing rapidly. These include copper and copper articles, fish and crustaceans, machinery and ready-made garments. Interestingly, as evident from (Table 8), there appears to be a movement away from the primary sector towards value-added exports in Pakistan's offering to China in 2019 but for further details look. (Figure 3). And bilateral trades between Pakistan and China from 2015 to 2019 Top 15 products (Table 9).

Table 8 Pakistan's top 15 exports to China, 2019

<i>Product code</i>	<i>Product Label</i>	<i>Volume in 2019</i>	<i>Annual Growth in value b/w 2015-19, % p.a.</i>	<i>Share in Pakistan's exports, %</i>	<i>Equivalent ad valorem tariff faced by Pakistan</i>
TOTAL	<i>All products</i>	2,042,893	3	9	
52	<i>Cotton</i>	819,914	-9	25	7
74	<i>Copper and articles thereof</i>	308,951	108	87	1
10	<i>Cereals</i>	278,694	7	12	51
03	<i>Fish and crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic invertebrates</i>	135,807	32	29	5
26	<i>Ores, slag and ash</i>	86,372	3	92	0
17	<i>Sugars and sugar confectionery</i>	83,823	292	24	33
25	<i>Salt; Sulphur; earths and stone; plastering materials, lime and cement</i>	43,839	0	10	1
61	<i>Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted</i>	34,412	31	1	4
84	<i>Machinery, mechanical appliances, nuclear reactors, boilers; parts thereof</i>	29,828	86	11	2
41	<i>Raw hides and skins (other than furskins) and leather</i>	27,165	-9	12	4
23	<i>Residues and waste from the food industries; prepared animal fodder</i>	27,161	45	42	2
22	<i>Beverages, spirits and vinegar</i>	25,093	2	8	7
90	<i>Optical, photographic, cinematographic, measuring, checking, precision, medical or</i>	21,422	27	5	2

	<i>surgical . . .</i>				
62	<i>Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, not knitted or crocheted</i>	20,089	3	1	7
13	<i>Lac; gums, resins and other vegetable saps and extracts</i>	14,095	14	35	7

Source: ITC Trade Maps

Table 9: Bilateral trade between Pakistan and China from 2015 to 2019 Top 15 products

Product code	Product Category	Volume in 2015	Volume in 2016	Volume in 2017	Volume in 2018	Volume in 2019
52	<i>Cotton</i>	1,261,711	968,230	886,774	878,302	819,914
74	<i>Copper and articles thereof</i>	27,999	12,277	37,859	151,198	308,951
10	<i>Cereals</i>	167,050	220,821	95,655	162,310	278,694
03	<i>Fish and crustaceans, molluscs and other aquatic invertebrates</i>	46,168	47,993	60,189	91,782	135,807
26	<i>Ores, slag and ash</i>	70,649	77,664	98,599	67,312	86,372
17	<i>Sugars and sugar confectionery</i>	284	254	3,242	2,486	83,823
25	<i>Salt; sulphur; earths and stone; plastering materials, lime and cement</i>	47,977	37,436	38,524	43,628	43,839
61	<i>Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted</i>	11,862	16,911	22,112	30,697	34,412
84	<i>Machinery, mechanical appliances, nuclear reactors, boilers; parts thereof</i>	3,503	6,659	11,012	46,254	29,828
41	<i>Raw hides and skins (other than furskins) and leather</i>	42,133	37,120	37,097	35,299	27,165
23	<i>Residues and waste from the food industries; prepared animal fodder</i>	7,027	10,100	16,926	27,710	27,161
22	<i>Beverages, spirits and vinegar</i>	88,236	9,112	12,356	134,189	25,093
90	<i>Optical, photographic, cinematographic, measuring, checking, precision, medical or surgical . . .</i>	8,501	14,585	39,768	25,478	21,422
62	<i>Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, not knitted or crocheted</i>	17,951	20,077	20,251	21,360	20,089
13	<i>Lac; gums, resins and other vegetable saps and extracts</i>	10,297	5,804	13,361	11,194	14,095

Source: ITC Trade Maps

5.6. Exports and Imports of China from target countries

This research contains the latest international trade data for China, including service trade data, and tariffs:

In July 2020 China exported \$211B and imported \$173B, resulting in a positive trade balance of \$37.8B.

Between July 2019 and July 2020 the exports of China have increased by \$38.4B (22.3%) from \$172B to \$210.4B. (North American Academic Research, 4(2) | 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4506802> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 14

\$211B. While imports increased by \$17.4B (11.2%) from \$156B to \$173B. Trade: In July 2020 the top exports of China were Telephones (\$14.8B), Computers (\$13.4B), Other Cloth Articles (\$6.92B), Integrated Circuits (\$5.89B), and Light Fixtures (\$3.84B). In July 2020 the top imports of China were Integrated Circuits (\$29.4B), Crude Petroleum (\$14.1B), Iron Ore (\$10.9B), Soybeans (\$3.79B), and Refined Copper (\$3.29B). Figure 4 shows Exports and Imports of China from target countries in July 2020.

Figure 4. In July 2020 Exports and Imports of China from target countries

Source: Data from National Bureau of Statistics of China

Origins: In July 2020 the exports of China were mainly from Guangdong Province (\$48.7B), Zhejiang Province (\$35.3B), Jiangsu Province (\$32.2B), Shanghai Province (\$15B), and Shandong Province (\$14.7B). Figure 5 shows Exports and Imports of China from target countries in 2019.

While imports destinations were mainly Guangdong Province (\$32.3B), Shanghai Province (\$25.4B), Beijing (\$22.3B), Jiangsu Province (\$21.9B), and Shandong Province (\$11.7B).

Growth: In July 2020, the increase in China's year-by-year exports was explained primarily by an increase in exports to United States (\$6.33B or 16.9%), United Kingdom (\$3.89B or 99.3%), and Vietnam (\$3.02B or 44.2%), and product exports increase in Other Cloth Articles (\$6.34B or 1.11k %), Telephones (\$5.29B or 55.8%), and Computers (\$4.38B or 48.7%). In July 2020, the increase in China's year-by-year imports was explained primarily by an increase in imports from Taiwan (\$2.51B or 16.9%), Brazil (\$1.81B or 28.5%), and Japan (\$1.75B or 12.9%), and product imports increase in Crude Petroleum (\$3.36B or 31.2%), Integrated Circuits (\$3B or 11.4%), and Iron Ore (\$2.19B or 25.1%). **In 2019**, the value of merchandise exports from China totaled \$ 2.49 trillion. Merchandise exports from China increased by 0.173% compared to 2018. Goods exports grew up by \$ 4.33 billion in 2019 (the value of merchandise exports from China amounted to \$2.49 trillion in 2018). While, the value of merchandise imports to China totaled \$ 2.06 trillion

in 2019. Overall commodity imports to China decreased by 3.09% compared to 2018. Merchandise imports decreased by \$ 66 billion (the value of merchandise imports to China was equal to \$2.13 trillion in 2018).

Figure 5. In 2019 Exports and Imports of China from target countries

Source: Data from National Bureau of Statistics of China

In 2018 China was the number 2 economy in the world in terms of GDP (current US\$), the number 1 in total exports, the number 2 in total imports, and the number 30 most complex economy according to the Economic Complexity Index (ECI). In 2018, China exported \$2.59T and imported \$1.61T, resulting in a positive trade balance of \$977B. In 2018, China's exports per capita were \$1.86k and its imports per capita were \$1.16k. **Trade:** The top exports of China are Broadcasting Equipment (\$224B), Computers (\$147B), Office Machine Parts (\$100B), Integrated Circuits (\$90.9B), and Telephones (\$55.3B). The top imports of China are Crude Petroleum (\$208B), Integrated Circuits (\$133B), Iron Ore (\$59.2B), Cars (\$45.2B), and Petroleum Gas (\$44.2B). Figure 6 shows exports of China from target countries in July 2018.

Figure 6. In 2018 Exports and Imports of China from target countries

Source: Data from National Bureau of Statistics of China

In 2017, China's total imports and exports increased for the first time in three years, but this year's trade tensions with the United States and declining domestic demand are clouding the outlook. Exports are a key factor in China's economic expansion in 2017. According to data released by the General Administration of Customs, China's total export value increased by 7.9% to US\$2.26 trillion, the highest since 2011. Imports soared by 15.9% to US\$1.84 trillion, the largest increase in six years. Here, we discussed China's top five import and export countries from target countries in 2017. In December 2017, China's exports increased by 10.9% year-on-year to USD 231.8 billion, down from 12.3% last month. Imports rose 4.5% from the previous month to US\$177.1 billion, lower than the 17.7% increase in November and the lowest level in a year. Figure 7 shows exports of China from target countries in July 2017.

Figure 7. In July 2017 Exports and Imports of China from target countries

Source: Data from National Bureau of Statistics of China

In 2016, China stood first in exports with a share of 17% of world exports. The total volume of China's exports in 2016 was 5.291 trillion dollars. In terms of exports, Germany is the large export partner of China from Europe and Saudi Arabia from Middle East countries. China mainly exports computer and broadcasting equipment to Germany and Saudi Arabia. Figure 5 represents the exports of China from selected countries from Middle East and Europe. Figure 8 shows exports of Pakistan from target countries in 2016. While, in 2016, China was the third major importer of goods in the world with a share of 12% of world imports. The total volume of China's imports in 2016 was 3.41 trillion dollars. Saudi Arabia and Germany are large import partners of China from Middle East and Europe countries, respectively. China mainly imports cars and vehicle parts from Germany and crude petroleum from Saudi Arabia. In Table 3 also represents the imports of China from selected countries from Middle East and Europe.

Figure 8. In 2016 Exports and Imports of China from target countries

Source: Data from National Bureau of Statistics of China

Figure 8 shows that China exports about \$26.4 billion to Saudi Arabia, \$4.99 billion to Kuwait, \$2.52 billion to Oman, \$104 billion to Germany, \$49.3 billion to France, and \$60.6 billion to the Netherlands. While, Figure 2 shows that China imports about \$23.7 billion from Saudi Arabia, \$6.19 billion from Kuwait, \$11.2 billion from Oman, \$98.8 billion from Germany, \$24.3 billion from France, and \$12.9 billion from the Netherlands.

5.7. Exports and Imports of Pakistan from target countries

This research contains the latest international trade data for Pakistan, including service trade data, and tariffs:

In 2019, The value of merchandise exports from Pakistan totaled \$ 23 billion. Merchandise exports from Pakistan increased by 0.498% compared to 2018. Goods exports grew up by \$ 117 million in 2019 (the value of merchandise exports from Pakistan amounted to \$23 billion in 2018). While, the value of merchandise imports to Pakistan totaled \$ 50 billion in 2019. Overall commodity imports to Pakistan decreased by 16.7% compared to 2018. Merchandise imports decreased by \$ 10 billion (the value of merchandise imports to Pakistan was equal to \$60 billion in 2018).

Exports structure from Pakistan in 2019 represented by the following main commodity groups:

- 17% (4.05 billion US\$): 63 - Other made-up textile articles; sets; worn clothing and worn textile articles; rags
- 13.6% (3.24 billion US\$): 52 - Cotton
- 12.7% (3.01 billion US\$): 61 - Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted

- 11.8% (2.8 billion US\$): 62 - Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, not knitted or crocheted
- 9.97% (2.36 billion US\$): 10 - Cereals
- 2.66% (632 million US\$): 42 - Articles of leather; saddlery and harness; travel goods, handbags and similar containers; articles of animal gut (other than silkworm gut)
- 1.98% (472 million US\$): 03 - Fish and crustaceans, mollusk's and other aquatic invertebrates
- 1.9% (452 million US\$): 90 - Optical, photographic, cinematographic, measuring, checking, precision, medical or surgical instruments and apparatus; parts and accessories thereof
- 1.82% (433 million US\$): 25 - Salt; sulfur; earths and stone; plastering materials, lime and cement
- 1.67% (397 million US\$): 08 - Edible fruit and nuts; peel of citrus fruit or melons.

Figure 9. In 2019 Exports of Pakistan from target countries

Source: Data from UN Comtrade

Imports structure to Pakistan in 2019 represented by the following main commodity groups:

- 28% (14.3 billion US\$): 27 - Mineral fuels, mineral oils and products of their distillation; bituminous substances; mineral waxes
- 9.42% (4.71 billion US\$): 84 - Nuclear reactors, boilers, machinery and mechanical appliances; parts thereof
- 8.49% (4.25 billion US\$): 85 - Electrical machinery and equipment and parts thereof; sound recorders and reproducers, television image and sound recorders and reproducers, and parts and accessories of such articles
- 6.18% (3.09 billion US\$): 72 - Iron and steel
- 4.71% (2.36 billion US\$): 29 - Organic chemicals
- 4.42% (2.21 billion US\$): 39 - Plastics and articles thereof

- 3.86% (1.93 billion US\$): 15 - Animal or vegetable fats and oils and their cleavage products prepared edible fats; animal or vegetable waxes
- 2.93% (1.46 billion US\$): 87 - Vehicles other than railway or tramway rolling stock, and parts and accessories thereof
- 2.43% (1.22 billion US\$): 12 - Oil seeds and oleaginous fruits; miscellaneous grains, seeds and fruits; industrial or medicinal plants; straw and fodder
- 1.66% (832 million US\$): 52 – Cotton. Figure 10 shows Imports of Pakistan from target countries in 2019.

Figure 10. In 2019 Imports of Pakistan from target countries

Source: Data from UN Comtrade

In 2018 Pakistan was the number 39 economy in the world in terms of GDP (current US\$), the number 69 in total exports, the number 49 in total imports, and the number 104 most complex economy according to the Economic Complexity Index (ECI). In 2018, Pakistan exported \$26.7B and imported \$61.5B, resulting in a negative trade balance of -\$34.8B. In 2018, Pakistan's exports per capita were \$126 and its imports per capita were \$290. During the last five reported years the exports of Pakistan have changed by -\$1.73B from \$28.4B in 2013 to \$26.7B in 2018. Similarly, during the last five reported years the imports of Pakistan changed by \$16.3B from \$45.2B in 2013 to \$61.5B in 2018.

Trade: The top exports of Pakistan are House Linens (\$3.5B), Rice (\$1.98B), Non-Knit Men's Suits (\$1.62B), Non-Retail Pure Cotton Yarn (\$1.25B), and Heavy Pure Woven Cotton (\$989M). The top imports of Pakistan are Refined Petroleum (\$5.76B), Crude Petroleum (\$4.16B), Petroleum Gas (\$3.28B), Palm Oil (\$1.98B), and Scrap Iron (\$1.41B). Figure 11 shows exports of Pakistan from target countries in 2018.

Similarly, Figure 12 shows Imports of Pakistan from target countries in 2018.

Figure 11. In 2018 Exports of Pakistan from target countries

Source: Data from UN Comtrade

Figure 12. In 2018 Imports of Pakistan from target countries

Source: Data from UN Comtrade

In 2017, According to the provisional figures compiled by the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, exports from Pakistan during February, 2017 amounted to Rs.171,511 million (provisional) as against Rs. 186,384 million (provisional) in January, 2017 and Rs.186,870 million during February, 2016 showing a decrease of 7.98% over January,2017 and of 8.22% over February, 2016.

- In terms of US dollars, the exports in February, 2017 was \$ 1,638 million (provisional) as compared to \$ 1,780 million (provisional) in January, 2017 showing a decrease of 7.98% and by 8.29% as compared to \$ 1,786 million in February, 2016.
- Exports during July - February, 2016 - 2017 totaled Rs.1,394,005 million (provisional) as against. Rs.1, 441,936 million during the corresponding period of last year showing a decrease of 3.32%.
- In terms of US dollars, the exports during July – February, 2016 - 2017 totaled \$ 13,318 million (provisional) against \$ 13,859 million during the corresponding period of last year showing a decrease of 3.90%.
- Main commodities of exports during February, 2017 were Readymade garments (Rs.20,685 million), Knitwear (Rs.18,561 million), Bedwear (Rs.18,366 million), Cotton cloth (Rs.16,374 million), Rice others (Rs.12,116 million), Cotton yarn (Rs.9,852 million), Towels (Rs.6,722 million), Made-up articles (excl. towels & bedwear) (Rs.5,447 million) Fruits (Rs.4,354 million) and Rice basmati (Rs.4,265 million).
- The increase (+) / decrease (-) recorded in main commodities exported during February, 2017 over January, 2017 and February, 2016 is given below in Table 10. Similarly, Figure 13 shows the 2017 exports of Pakistan from the target's countries.

Table 10. January, 2017 and February, 2016 data

Sr. No	COMMODITIES	%Change for value in million Rupees in February, 2017 over	
		February, 2016	January, 2017
1	Readymade Garments	5.37	-2.23
2	Knitwear	2.15	-11.23
3	Bedwear	2.76	1.24
4	Cotton cloth	-14.68	-15.83
5	Rice others	-19.68	-9.89
6	Cotton yarn	-11.39	1.47
7	Towels	-3.78	1.05
8	Made up articles (excl. towels & bedwear)	2.31	-5.09
9	Fruits	-34.21	-31.79
10	Rice basmati	8.28	14.62

Figure 13. In 2017 Exports of Pakistan from Target Countries

Source: Data from UN Comtrade

Imports into Pakistan during February, 2017 amounted to Rs.462, 764 million (provisional) as against Rs. 494,721 million (provisional) in January, 2017 and Rs.343, 206 million during February, 2016 showing a decrease of 6.46% over January, 2017 but an increase of 34.84% over February, 2016.

- In terms of US dollars, the imports in February, 2017 was \$ 4,419 million (provisional) as compared to \$ 4,724 million (provisional) in January, 2017 showing a decrease of 6.46% but increased by 34.73% as compared to \$ 3,280 million in February, 2016
- Imports during July - February, 2016 - 2017 totaled Rs.3, 505,990 million (provisional) as against Rs.3, 006,699 million during the corresponding period of last year showing an increase of 16.61%.
- In terms of US dollars, the imports during July - February, 2016 - 2017 totaled \$ 33,495 million (provisional) as against \$ 28,898 million during the corresponding period of last year showing an increase of 15.91%.
- Main commodities of imports during February, 2017 were Petroleum products (Rs.49,062 million), Petroleum crude (Rs.23,873 million), Power generating machinery (Rs.23,487 million), Electrical machinery & apparatus (Rs.21,053 million), Palm oil (Rs.17,888 million), Iron & steel (Rs.17,614 million), Plastic materials (Rs.17,545 million), Natural gas, liquified (Rs.14,577 million), Raw cotton (Rs.13,454 million) and Pulses (Leguminous vegetables) Rs.11,345 million)
- The increase (+) / decrease (-) recorded in main commodities imported during February, 2017 over January, 2017 and February, 2016 are given below in Table 11:

Table 11. January, 2017 and February, 2016 data

Sr. No	COMMODITIES	%Change for value in million Rupees in February, 2017 over	
		February, 2016	January, 2017
1	Petroleum products	46.60	-9.70
2	Petroleum crude	83.84	19.59
3	Power generating machinery	40.62	-19.08
4	Electrical machinery & apparatus	60.50	-24.51
5	Palm oil	26.88	-0.67
6	Iron & Steel	0.10	-7.35
7	Plastic materials	27.52	2.47
8	Natural gas, liquified	186.61	53.90
9	Raw cotton	31.28	123.08
10	Pulses (Leguminous vegetables)	116.26	-9.56

BALANCE OF TRADE

Based on the provisional figures of imports and exports the balance of trade in February, 2017 was (-) 291,253 million in terms of Rupees and (-) 2,781 million in US dollars. The balance of trade figures cumulative from July - February, 2016 - 2017 were (-) 2,111,985 million in terms of Rupees and (-) 20,177 million in US dollars. Four statements giving quantity and value details of selected commodities of exports and imports for the month of February, 2017 and July - February, 2016 - 2017 along-with the data for previous month and corresponding period of last year are enclosed. Figure 14 shows the 2017 Imports of Pakistan Targets in the Countries.

Figure 14. In 2017 Imports of Pakistan from Target Countries

Source: Data from UN Comtrade

Pakistan's exports from 2015 to 2016 were 21 billion U.S. dollars and imports were 44.76 billion U.S. dollars. Pakistan's exports have increased from US\$7.5 billion in 1999 to US\$18 billion in the 2007-2008 fiscal years, an increase of more than 100%. Pakistan exports rice, kinnows, mango, furniture, cotton fiber, cement, ceramic tiles, marble, textiles, clothing, leather products, veterinary surgery supplies, sporting goods (famous for football), tableware, surgical instruments, household appliances, software, carpets, Floor mats, ice cream, beef, chicken, milk powder, wheat, shellfish (especially shrimp/prawns), vegetables, processed food, Suzuki assembled in Pakistan (shipped to Afghanistan and other countries), defense equipment (submarine), tanks, radar) , Salt, onyx, engineering items and many other items. Pakistan produces cement and exports it to Asia and the Middle East. In August 2007, Pakistan began to export cement to India to fill the shortage caused by the boom in the construction industry. Russia is a growing market for Pakistani exporters. In 2009/2010, Pakistan's export target is US\$20 billion. As of April 2015, Pakistan's exports reached US\$29 billion.

Pakistan seeks extensive cooperation with China in geographical areas and products. In an interview with China Economic Net, the consultant said that the Chinese government has given Pakistan an opportunity to not only export textiles, leather and agricultural products, but the country will now also export chemical and engineering products. He told China Economic Net: "We think this is an excellent opportunity to improve cooperation with Chinese companies. The second phase of the free trade agreement between Pakistan and China will be implemented from December 1." According to statistics, according to the agreement the 313 product lines exempt from tariffs will cover Pakistani products worth nearly US\$2 billion exported to China each year. According to data compiled by the National Bank of Pakistan, from July 2018 to June 2019, Pakistan's revised total exports to China increased by US\$106 million in the previous fiscal year, with a growth potential of approximately 20 times. When asked whether Pakistan's exports to China are likely to increase 10 times by the end of the fiscal year after the second phase of the North American Free Trade Agreement is implemented, Dawood said: "I hope so. This is something we absolutely want to do." "I look forward to this growth. We are very interested in improving exports to China.

5.8. Potential of boosting Pakistan's exports and Imports

There are many benefits to trade with China. Currently, China is the second largest market for Pakistani products, with a 7% share, while the United States accounts for 16.7% of total exports. China is also the country's second largest source of imports. Due to the signing of the Free Trade Agreement (FTA), exports to China have increased. As a result of the free trade policy, trade growth increased from 19% to 26%. The Chinese government has shown great interest in expanding trade with Pakistan. He hopes to import more products from Pakistan. China is expected to import vegetables and fruits. Pakistan imports machinery, but the industrial infrastructure needs a lot of development to achieve profitable production. In China, there is a huge demand for Pakistani mangoes, berries, potatoes, wheat, rice and citrus. The two countries are also

committed to the development of genetically modified rice. Another big project is to establish a reliable halal food supply chain.

Windows of Opportunities

In China, there are specific opportunities for Pakistan in the agriculture sector as the country is facing problems with the quality of its irrigated land area. It is getting scarce. For some crops, this situation is very serious. China prefers to conduct agricultural trade with Asian countries such as Pakistan, India, Thailand and Vietnam to meet its agricultural needs. Due to high tariffs, rice trade between Thailand and China is difficult. Pakistan seized the opportunity and filled the gap in the market. This was a success. Pakistan is the largest exporter of cotton to China and later became the second largest exporter of rice to Beijing.

There is another important area, covering minerals and gems (precious stones). Under the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) project, tariffs have been reduced from 35% to 0%. Now, the gold and copper reservoirs discovered at Reko Diq have also become the focus of Chinese engineers. Due to quarantine issues in potential importing countries, China has indicated that it may import CPEC products in the agricultural and horticultural sectors.

Barriers and Advantages

Pakistan will do its best to increase trade with China. There are specific issues that hinder implementation. Most of Pakistan's exports are sold to Europe and the United States, but China is Pakistan's main export destination. Pakistan's main raw materials exported to China. Cotton and hard chrome account for 66% of exports. This has not changed for a while. Unlike other countries that trade with China which is FTA, Pakistan has a great advantage. It provides growth potential for many Pakistani products. The free trade agreement with China should give Pakistan an advantage over other countries in several potentially highly profitable products such as textiles and sporting goods. However, due to non-tariff barriers, the country has been unable to enter this huge market.

In most products with great potential, Pakistani exporters have not made progress due to non-tariff barriers. The obstacles identified by the World Trade Organization (WTO) are expensive and time-consuming bureaucratic procedures, lack of commercial judicial institutions, lack of transparency, and irregular tenders. In addition, unlike other Pakistani trading partners, there is a communication gap between the two countries. This has aroused suspicion among the traders of the two countries because they cannot understand each other's expectations and lack confidence due to the lack of transitional factors. Once the transaction is cancelled or a bad experience occurs, it is difficult for the lost party to regain trust.

China is a big market, and sometimes you will see insufficient supply in Pakistan. China needs to import because of the shortage of labor market in China. The high cost makes it difficult to compete with foreign competitors. There is a marketing problem. Pakistan needs to emphasize the business opportunities in the

CPEC project, because many traders in the two countries do not fully understand this. Due to this shortcoming, local businessmen and foreign residents cannot obtain several opportunities. Several reports pointed out those Pakistani businessmen felt uncomfortable after in-depth investigations of their products, which sometimes destroyed the goods. This is because Pakistani products are not highly regarded in China.

6. Conclusion

China is a country which is developing very speedily. In previously China had signed two FTA one in 2006 that's was trade in goods and trade in services in 2009. The first FTA more was focused on the to get duties free access to Chinese market on cotton, fabrics, leather goods, iron and steel, sports goods, industrial alcohol etcetera, while on the other hand Pakistan give to China machinery, chemical, food, vegetables, Raw materials and industries sectors. The second FTA was more comprehensive and allowed trade and goods investment in services sectors. The aim of this project is to start in investment regime infrastructure, education, tourism, IT and environmental services. Pakistan had allowed market access to China in eleven sectors, one hundred sub sectors while China had committed to Pakistan access to eleven sectors and over 130 sub sectors, so china give market access to Pakistan more than give to another countries however later Chinese government committed more concession to ASEAN Countries where Pakistan had comparative advantage so it's kind of profits agreement and benefits for Pakistan. Despite the unsuccessful signed FTA living up the mark both parties have thoughtfully concluded second FTA and which china has agreed to provide duties free excessive and unilateral concession to 313 Pakistani products line (an increase of 257 tariff lines) over the next fifteen years.

Moreover, under the new FTA Pakistan were commissioned approximately 65% of its market with Chinese exports where china is open up 90% of its market for Pakistani exports also allowing the liberalization of 75% trade line and 90% trade values in the FTA has been agreed and this also help in remedying the colossal trade deficit between the two countries, which was around 10 billion USD last year and as we know that China is the world largest importers and provide the world largest market for exports . China annually imports figure stands out at USD 2 trillion where as 64\$ billion of its imports are what Pakistan produce. Until July 2018 Pakistan exports to China average around 1.2 billion per annum 120 to 150 million per month USD exports improve to about 200 million dollars per month from July 2018 to March 2019, However, even if Pakistan manages to capture 10% share of those \$64 billion Chinese imports, it can experience a significant increment in exports reaching up to \$6.5 billion. In a nutshell the recently signed FTA between Pakistan and china yield a splendid opportunity for the two nations so amazing amid the national and global economic tranquility and the government having the fancy to shifty Pakistan from consumption orientated to the export and economy the culmination of the second phase of FTA is none less than a silver lining for Pakistan. In this paper we concerns about Pakistani government and also from their business circle of the Pakistan but for this usual I would like to say that for their Chinese government because the China now either were the factory so he has become their largest trading partner for over 100

countries in the world so for China he never has the intention to seek their trade surplus with their any other trading companies let alone iron brothers so I think the main fundamental reason behind that this Cheetah imbalance is that's structural problem was a pity us because for our channel we have a strong manufacturing base so it's exports more high value product to Pakistan but we import lower relatively lower value the mostly primary goods from the Pakistan to China that's the main reason why there is a big imbalance between us so that's the first question Chinese government put more attention on this issue so after you level round of negotiations we finished the finalize their the phase FTA 2 between both countries.

Moreover, china has become the biggest partner for Pakistan for their consecutive with physical years and also China is the second imported destination for their Pakistan for also for five consecutive years so that's the first issue and the second is about their face to FTA in this era protocol Chinese government gave some special arrangements and to take consideration seriously over their request or concerns from Pakistani government now is the level of trade liberalization has risen substantially from the previously 35% to now 75% so and in the breakdown in terms of the trade volume China provide 90% of their zero duty to Pakistani products china and they received their 67 percent order zero duty product. So that is the shoulder or attitudes or their concretes efforts to solvent there the issues related to their trading. The Pakistani government has adopt pro-business policies so in this study we hope to this industrial policy could be adopted very quickly and the tool to do a lot more in their ease of doing business and to improve our greetings business climate and also for investor so if a more foreign and Chinese investor can come to invest in Pakistan there we will help a beauty of manufacturing capacity and strong and fundamental foundation for export expansion in the world and also including to the Chinese market so we hope China and Pakistan work closely together with Pakistani federal and local government.

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Data availability statement

Some or all data, models, or code that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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